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of **EXPRESSION**
A Creative Folio

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The Thought of You

I think of you to start my day
When it is time for me to pray
I pray for grace to keep me strong
And keep you near though not for long

I think of you as in a song
Although unsung you know the tune
It breaks my heart you are not here
To sing for me with loving care

Back in my mind your voice is clear
Humming a tune I cannot hear
When days are laden with heavy stifles
The thought of you would ease my life

In every leaf my garden has
It bears your face with radiant blush
Your walls the hills, your roof the stars
They, too, surround me where you are

When emptiness sets in with gloom
Your winsome smile fills up my room
With sparkling eyes, you light my day
I love to think of you that way